

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Preparation of Fluoroalkyl End-capped Oligomer/Magnetite Nanocomposites – Application to Water/Oil Separation

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Preparation of Fluoroalkyl End-capped Vinyltrimethoxysilane Oligomeric Silica/Magnetite Composites

Average particle
size: 10 nm
40 nm
200 nm

Fig. Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM) image of the $\text{R}_F\text{-(VM-SiO}_2\text{)}_n\text{-R}_F/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ composites

a) Particle size of the used Fe_3O_4 : 10 nm

b) Feed ratio of $\text{R}_F\text{-(VM)}_n\text{-R}_F/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ (mg/mg): 100/100

*Superoleophilic/Superhydrophobic
Characteristic!*

Adsorption process of oil (blue-colored dodecane) on the water surface by the $R_F-(VM-SiO_2)_n-R_F/Fe_3O_4$ nanocomposite powders under a magnetic field

(A): Original Fe_3O_4 ;
particle size of the
used Fe_3O_4 : 10 nm

Original Fe_3O_4

Permanent magnet

(B): particle size of the
used Fe_3O_4 : 10 nm

$R_F-(VM-SiO_2)_n-R_F$
 $/Fe_3O_4$
nanocomposite

Permanent magnet

